

PSYCHOLOGICAL PECULIARITIES OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE DEVELOPMENT IN JUNIOR SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Abstract: in this article the authors describe in detail emotional intelligence and its mechanisms of development in primary school children. The characteristic of emotional intelligence as an important factor of psychological and emotional ability of a person is given.

Key words: emotion, emotional intelligence, preschooler, school, ability.

Nowadays, the problem of connection between feelings and reason, emotional and rational, their interaction and mutual influence is of great interest. Scientists have determined that about 80% of success in social and personal spheres of life determines the level of development of emotional intelligence, and only 20% - IQ - intelligence quotient, which determines the level of mental abilities of a person [4]. Emotional intelligence reflects the inner world of a person, determines his/her behaviour and interaction with other people. People with a high level of development of emotional intelligence have a pronounced ability to understand their own emotions and emotions of other people, to manage the emotional sphere, which provides higher adaptability and efficiency in communication.

In spite of this, most of the educational process is aimed at the cognitive development of the student, while the emotional life of the child and the ability to build relationships with other people are out of the scope of the organised pedagogical process.

Emotional intelligence is the ability to understand and manage one's own and others' emotions. There are two components in the structure of emotional intelligence: intrapersonal (the ability to understand and manage one's own emotions); interpersonal (the ability to understand and manage other people's emotions) [3].

The ability to understand emotions means that a person:

- can recognise an emotion, i.e. identify the fact that he/she or another person is experiencing an emotion;
- can identify an emotion, i.e. identify what emotion he/she or another person is experiencing and find a verbal expression for it;
- understands the causes of the emotion and the consequences that will result. The ability to manage emotions means that a person:
 - can control the intensity of emotion, primarily by muting excessively strong emotions;
 - can control the external expression of emotions;
 - can, if necessary, arbitrarily cause this or that emotion [3].

The development of emotional intelligence is of particular importance and relevance in the younger school age, because it is during this period that children are actively developing

emotionally, improving their self-awareness, the ability to reflect and the ability to take the position of a partner, to take into account their needs and feelings. The importance of emotions in the younger school age is very great, both in mental activity and in the formation of the child's personality. They enrich the psyche, brightness and variety of feelings, make him more interesting for others and for himself. The variety of one's own experiences helps to understand more deeply and subtly what is going on.

During a child's primary school education, the child's organism develops intensively. When a primary school child enters school, his or her lifestyle changes, new goals appear, and all this leads to significant changes in the child's emotional life. In contrast to the preschool age, junior schoolchildren have new experiences, new tasks and goals arise, a new emotional attitude to aspects of reality and phenomena occurring around him. At first it is difficult for a junior schoolboy to participate in learning activities at lessons, it is difficult for him to communicate with the teacher and the team in the learning process, as it requires great restraint in feelings. Gradually, younger pupils learn to control their behaviour, behave with more restraint in the process of fulfilling everyday school duties, requirements imposed on children by the teacher and later by the team.

The general orientation of emotions of junior schoolchildren is connected with the growth of awareness, restraint, stability of feelings and actions. The process and result of learning activities, the need for evaluation and good attitude of others is significant for junior schoolchildren, so most of the emotional reactions are directed to them, rather than to the game and communication with peers as it was observed in preschool age.

At school age there are situations that cause high situational anxiety in children, assessment situations such as answering at the blackboard, solving tests, passing exams. 85% of children in primary school experience a high level of anxiety in relation to knowledge testing, this is due to the fear of punishment and fear of upsetting parents. The second cause of anxiety is 'difficulties in learning'. Many schoolchildren experience anxiety during learning, both children with low grades and those who study well and even excellently, who are responsible for their studies and school discipline.

Inadequacy of a junior schoolboy to the level of requirements imposed by himself and parents in learning activities can lead to affects in behaviour, and in case of lack of attention from the teacher, can be consolidated as negative character traits. Such behaviour is characterised by an increase in general emotional excitability, symptoms and syndromes of fears, manifestation of aggression or negativism [5]. As a rule, children work very hard to achieve the highest mark, it is dangerous to breakdowns especially in case of sharp complication of activity. Such pupils have pronounced vegetative reactions, neurosis-like and psychosomatic disorders.

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Despite the fact that a junior schoolchild is emotionally responsive and reacts strongly to events, he/she starts to restrain his/her undesirable emotional reactions by willpower, tries to overcome strong excitement, for example, to hold back tears, to overcome his/her desires, obeying the teacher's demands. This leads to the fact that a junior schoolchild may not understand the emotion he/she is experiencing or portray an emotion he/she does not experience, i.e. there is a separation of expression from the experienced emotion both in one direction and another [2].

Younger pupils are easily 'infected' by the emotional feelings of others. Teachers are well aware of such facts, when laughter of some pupils causes laughter of other pupils in the class, although the latter may not know the reason for the laughter. Girls start crying when looking at a crying friend, not because they consider her unjustly offended, but because they see her tears. In addition, younger schoolchildren are very impressionable. Events seen in the theatre, cinema, experienced in the family, having a negative connotation lead to fear, fright. These events can be fixed in the child's memory for a long time and disturb him, thus distracting him from the learning process.

Schoolchildren of younger grades, as shown by T.B. Piskareva, more easily understand emotions arising in familiar life situations, but find it difficult to put their emotional experiences into words. They are better at distinguishing positive emotions than negative ones. It is difficult for them to distinguish between fear and surprise. Unlike preschoolers, who prefer to perceive only cheerful and joyful pictures, junior schoolchildren have the ability to empathise when perceiving harsh scenes and dramatic conflicts [1].

Thus, for successful adaptation in society a person must have a developed emotional intelligence, which is the readiness of a person to orientate on another person and take into account his emotional state in his activities. The following features of development of emotional intelligence in younger schoolchildren can be distinguished: easy responsiveness to events; directness and frankness of expressing their feelings; great emotional instability; weak awareness of their own and other people's emotions and feelings. These features should be taken into account in the educational process.

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